

A Review on Diesel Homogeneous Charge Compression Ignition Engine

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Received: July 15, 2018, Accepted: August 24, 2018, Published: August 24, 2018.

ABSTRACT

Nowadays the Automotive industries are facing the problem of improving the fuel economy and lower emissions. The homogeneous charge compression ignition (HCCI) is an advanced combustion technology that is cleaner and more proficient than alternate kinds of combustion. This paper presents the experimental results regarding HCCI, engine. HCCI engine provides better fuel conversion efficiency and low NO_x emission, but nevertheless it has some fundamental issues, for example, concession combustion phase control, controlled auto-ignition, operating range, preparation of homogeneous charge, cold start and emissions of unburned hydrocarbon (UHC), and carbon monoxide (CO) should be defeated for effective process of HCCI engine. Most of the researcher worked out in preparation of homogeneous fuel-air mixture. The main objective of this paper is to provide review on the HCCI external mixture formation and (Direct Injection) DI-HCCI methods. The various methods of combustion phase control by HCCI combustion are also discussed in this paper.

Keywords: HCCI, stratified charge compression ignition (SCCI), low temperature combustion (LTC), Emissions, Direct Injection.

1. INTRODUCTION

Internal combustion engines are the main sources for automotive industries. Engines create control by expending an enormous measure of fuel by combustion, and emit harmful exhaust emissions, for example, unburned hydrocarbon (UHC), carbon monoxide (CO), carbon dioxide (CO₂), oxides of nitrogen (NO_x), and soot issue [1]. The vehicle populace is extending exponentially because of the quick change in the populace. The emission enactments additionally end up plainly stringent. The primary assignment for the researchers, scientists, specialists and intellect is to get an explanation to decrease the engine out flow, and powerful usage of energy. Later most recent two decades, several vehicular industries bring together numerous present automotive vehicles, for the most part to high fuel economy, minimize the emissions, and to utilize altered alternative fuels. In such way, the investigators and architects gave careful consideration towards the propelled methods of combustion like HCCI, stratified charge compression ignition (SCCI), and low temperature combustion (LTC) as the consequences of predominant fuel change efficiencies and ultra-low emissions of NO_x and soot.[2]

Figure 1. HCCI Combustion instantaneous decrease of NO_x and soot [6]

Figure 2. HCCI combustion is a combination of SI and CI combustion methods [6]

Among these, the HCCI engines can possibly chance the severe emission measures (EURO VI) and CO₂ emission criteria [4,5]. Fig. 1 shows the district of HCCI combustion great over the unburned hydrocarbon/carbon monoxide oxidation breaking point and rescues the betterment of both NO_x and PM. The HCCI combustion is thought to be a standout amongst other combustion innovations to be received more extensive in the demand not so distant future, as it offers a broad selection of fuel versatility [11] with higher fuel conversion efficiency, and low emissions. Fuel flexibility is more over made reference to as a potential favourable position. The arranging of lean homogeneous mixture and low temperature combustion (LTC) are received in HCCI innovation to smother the NO_x and PM emissions from the engine. Fig. 2 shows the similarity of SI, CI and HCCI performances. In HCCI engines, a lean homogeneous combustible mixture (fuel-air equivalence ratio $\Phi < 1$) is arranged, before the beginning of ignition and auto ignited as an importance of temperature increase in the compression stroke. [3]

The HCCI working is indistinguishable to spark ignition engine which utilizes the homogeneous charge for burning and in the same way to compression ignition engine that takes the auto ignition of the blend. Subsequently, HCCI is the combination of SI and CI combustion processes. In SI engines, three areas of combustion, specifically the burnt area unburned area and a thin flame reaction area amidst for turbulent flame spread over the

cylinder. In CI engines, fuel is dispersed inside the cylinder and a particular dissemination flame goes within the cylinder [7]. In HCCI engine combustion self-started ignition of the whole cylinder charge happens without any dissemination flame or flame front spread. The contrast of various parameters affecting the combustion methods in SI, CI, and HCCI are known in Table 1&2. [2]

Table 1. Difference between traditional SI Engine and HCCI Engine.

Basic of comparison		SI Engine		HCCI Engine
Ignition method		Spark ignition		Auto ignition
Ignition point		Single		Multi points
Fuel economy		Good		Best
Injection type		Port injection		Both port and direct injection
Max efficiency		30%		More than 40%
Throttle loss		More		No
Equivalence ratio		1		Less than 1
Compression ratio		Low		High
Combustion duration		More		Less
Major emissions	HC,CO	And NOx		HC and CO

Table 2: Comparison between Diesel Engine and HCCI Engine

Basic of comparison	Diesel Engine	HCCI Engine
Ignition Type	Direct injection	Both port and direct injection
Max efficiency	40%	More than 40%
Fuel economy	Better	Best
Combustion temperatures	1900-2100K	800-1100K
Combustion duration	More	Less
Major emissions	NOx, PM and HC	HC and CO

Engines are worked in the district of lower equivalence ratios to enhance efficiency and decrease emissions. Because of huge rise in the vehicle populace, the advanced combustion technology is utilized principally in IC engines. The NOx discharge can be entire just by lessening the flame temperature of combustion. Lean burns engines form brings down temperatures, which is the main influence to decrease the creation of NOx. The excess air utilized in lean burning outcomes in a more total ignition of the fuel, which decreases both the UHC and CO emissions. The HCCI engines are worked in auto-ignite off the fuel by the compression as the piston proceeds to the top dead center. The engine must be worked on a variable compression ratio (VCR) to change the auto-ignition of the cylinder charge close to the TDC. An extensive change of fuels can be burnt effectively by implementing the VCR system. A part of alternate strategies for fuel adaptability for the given engine are charge heating [16], boost pressure, exhaust gas re-use variable valve actuation (VVA) etc. [2]

HCCI

The mixture planning in HCCI engines is a critical parameter and it can be accomplished by utilizing either port fuel injection or port fuel injection with diesel vaporizer that prompts a homogeneous charge mixture. Common rail Direct injection

(CRDI) is another technique embraced, where fuel can be injected very early in the compressor stroke or at a later stage under high pressure to accomplish a homogeneous mixture. The most widely recognized techniques embraced to encourage auto-ignition of the blend should be possible by expanding the compression ratio, heating the charge, exhaust gas recirculation and utilizing blends of mixes.

Methods of preparation of external mixture

A few researchers presented an electronically precise fuel vaporizer used on behalf of low volatility and high boiling point fuel certain a diesel. The diesel vaporizer designed a precise aspect and dispersed aerosol using a quick evaporation because of a better surface to volume ratio. The smoke emissions were expressed to be insignificant and the exhaust gas re-use was used for ignition control and the NOx outflows. The process temperature of vaporizer is over the boiling point of fuel for effective preparation of an outside mixture (8,9,10).

Ganesh et al. [8] studied the performance and emission characteristics of the HCCI with port fuel injection method aided by fuel vaporizer on a single cylinder, air cooled DI diesel engine. Cooled EGR (30°C) in 10, 20 and 30% amount was applied to control the early ignition. The results concluded that at

30% EGR rate given low NO_x, smoke emissions and poor fuel economy.

Singh et al. [9] focused on the relative air–fuel ratios and EGR rates. Results given that, at $\lambda > 3.70$ with noiseless and smooth engine process.

G.Nagarajan et al. [10] had conducted experiments to investigate HCCI mode and DI diesel and DI biodiesel mode of operation. The results given that, ignition delay reduced due to better mixture preparation. Also, huge decrease in NO_x and smoke emissions with 10% exhaust gas recirculation. The experimental conditions of authors [8-10] is presented in Table 3 and Figure 3.

Table.3 Overview of Approaches of Outside mixture preparation after literature

Researcher	Used as fuel	Preparation of homogeneous charge technique	Advantages	Disadvantages
D. Ganesh et al [8]	Diesel	Fuel vaporizer with Port fuel injection	90-98% of NO _x emissions were decreased and gives good fuel efficiency	The UHC emission was more due to poor combustion efficiency.
Singh et al [9]	Diesel	Diesel fuel vaporizer	Air–fuel ratios ($\lambda = 4.95, 3.70$ and 2.56) At $\lambda > 3.70$ Reduced NO _x and smoke emissions and lower maximum cylinder pressure	The UHC and CO emissions were more
G.Nagarajan et al[10]	Diesel	Diesel fuel vaporizer	NO _x and smoke emissions were reduced	-

Figure.3. Maximum EGR usage in single cylinder engine for HCCI

Port fuel injection

The port fuel injection is the easiest technique of preparation of outside mixture, in which injector is mounted in the intake manifold, near the intake valve. This method progresses the fuel distribution and volumetric efficiency through carburetion. The mixture goes into the cylinder a mid-engine suction and the turbulence made by intake flow enhances assist homogenization. Already stated strategy for blend arrangement has been expressed to be effective with petrol and alcoholic fuel. The primary impediment of this system is injection timing can't impact the beginning of ignition. Additionally, heavy fuels with lower volatility of PFI outcomes in poor vaporization in increased wall impact.

A few researchers utilized a more intake air temperature to vaporize the fuel in the intake manifold.

Maurya et al. [11] conducted experiments with port fuel injection method for preparing homogeneous mixture. Experiments were performed by altering the intake charge temperature (120-150^oc) and equivalence ratio (2.0-5.0) at constant speed 1500 rpm with a specific end goal to accomplish the stable HCCI ignition. As reported that at 120^oc, $\lambda = 2.5$ given better combustion characteristics, combustion efficiency and less NO_x emissions.

Agarwal et al. [12] have worked on HCCI engine fuelled with ethanol and methanol by changing the intake air temperatures. The results stated that, methanol and ethanol are the best substitutes for the petroleum fuels.

HarisankarBendu et al. [13] did Experiments on HCCI mode with Port fuel injection of ethanol. From the investigation, it was reported that, at 170^oC, the maximum value of combustion efficiency and brake thermal efficiency of ethanol was observed. Also reported that, the NO_x and smoke emissions were reduced.

S. Gowthaman et al. [14] conducted experiments with various inlet charge temperatures such as (80- 120^oC). From the investigation, it was found that smoke, CO and HC emissions were reduced but higher the specific fuel consumptions with expanding charge temperature about 100^oC.

Nagarajan et al. [15] have done experiments on HCCI engine with jatropha methyl ester fuel. Cooled EGR technique was adopted to control the early ignition of JME vapor-air mixture. From the investigation, it was observed that, 81% of NO_x and 72% of smoke emissions were reduced.

Ramesh et al. [16] carried out experiments to study the performance characteristics of acetylene fuel in HCCI engine. The result given that, the high fuel conversion efficiencies and extensive range of BMEPs. And also reported that, optimized EGR and control the inlet charge temperatures increase in brake thermal efficiency and knock, external charge heating were avoided.

AkhilendraPratap Singh et al. [17] worked on three dissimilar fuels like diesolin, diesohol, and diesosene to evaluate its particulate emission characteristics using modified fuels in HCCI mode, engine performance at different loads were discussed.

The experimental conditions of authors [11-17] is presented in Table 4 and Figure 4.

The difficulties involved in the external mixture formation such as Port fuel injection and Fuel vaporizer with Port fuel injection methods for fuel control during engine transients, combustion phase control and extended the operating load. So that another methodology common rail direct injection is to give better improvement compare to others methodology.

Table.4 Overview of Approaches of Outside mixture preparation after literature

Researcher	Used as fuel	Preparation of homogeneous charge technique	Advantages	Disadvantages
Maurya et al [11]	Ethanol	Port fuel injection	At 120 ⁰ , $\lambda = 2.5$ gives better combustion efficiency=97.47% and fuel conversion efficiency=44.78%, and NO _x emissions are lower than 10ppm was noticed	The CO emission was more due to higher air-fuel ratio.
Nagarajan et al [15]	Jatropha methyl ester	Port fuel injection	At EGR 30 ⁰ c cooled given 81% NO _x decreased and 72% decreased in smoke emission. And also reduced HC and CO.	-
Ramesh et al [16]	Acetylene	Manifold	NO _x and smoke emissions were reduced.	Limited to part load operation.
Akhilendrapratsingh et al [17]	Diesoline, Diesohol, Diesosene	Port fuel injection	It observed that Gasoline, alcohols and kerosene given better combustion, performance and reduced NO _x emissions.	-
Harisankar et al [13]	Ethanol	Port fuel injection	At 170 ⁰ c gives better combustion efficiency=98.2% and fuel conversion efficiency=43%, NO _x and smoke emissions were reduced.	The UHC and CO emissions were more.

Figure.4. Maximum usage inlet air temperature for HCCI

The difficulties involved in the external mixture formation such as Port fuel injection and Fuel vaporizer with Port fuel injection methods for fuel control during engine transients, combustion phase control and extended the operating load. So that another methodology common rail direct injection is to give better improvement compare to others methodology.

Common rail Direct injection method

Numerous researchers have shown comprehensive experimentally on the common rail DI-HCCI to extend the operating load and the combustion phase controlled and also additional reduces the soot and NO_x emission to nearly zero level with a little lower brake fuel conversion efficiency.

Pranab Das et al. [18] concentrated on combustion control approach for DI-HCCI combustion using a dual injection method. The results revealed that, NO_x and smoke emissions were reduced and extended experiment [19] by using two injection strategies with blends of n-heptane and isooctane fuel. It was found that the most critical output is that a two phase's heat release pattern is observed in high cetane fuel. And also stated that the quantity of isooctane is increased, low temperature

heat release part reduces and peak heat release rate, peak pressure rise rate and SOC moves away from the TDC due to longer preparation phase. And also concluded that, cetane number shows a main role in combustion phasing controlling and emission behaviour of the DI-HCCI combustion engine. Caninar et al. [20] studied the impacts of utilization of DEE on the combustion and outflow emissions in a DI-HCCI engine. The results shown that single phase ignition observed by adding of premixed DEE fuel, and also found that the reduced NO_x and soot emissions. Qiang fang et al. [21] investigated the effects of EGR and pilot injection amount on engine performance and emission. The results reported that, increase the pilot injection amount and low range of EGR rates decreases NO_x and soot emissions. Junjun Ma et al. [22] focused on the possessions of premixed ratio and DI timing. The results revealed that the increasing the premixed ratios and effective enhanced the brake, fuel conversion efficiency at low to medium load and NO_x emissions were decreased. Wang et al. [23] explored the impacts of dimethyl ether (DME) blended with diesel on the combustion and outflow emissions in a DI-HCCI engine. The results given that, better performance with DME blended fuelled engine and observed that, NO_x and soot emissions were controlled the common rail system with two or more injection methods. Zaidi et al. [24] a diesel engine was modified to operate as an electronically controlled DI-HCCI engine. The results given that, the fuel consumption decreased by 20-30% and also reduced NO_x emissions. Lee et al. [25] studied the single-pilot injection and double pilot injection methods with extensive injection timing, variety different injection amount ratios and several dwell times. The results revealed that the single- pilot injection is the best method to reduce the NO_x and smoke emissions compare to other.

Techniques of HCCI Combustion control

The combustion control of the HCCI mode engine is one of the testing factors in HCCI advancement. These difficulties ought to be annihilated for the effective process of HCCI engine. The real difficulties are controlling the auto ignition temperature of the blend, confine the rate of heat release at high load operation, and exhaust emissions control and decreasing the knocking. The HCCI combustion can be more precise by preheat the inlet air, pressurized inlet air, variable compression ratio, variation of valve timing, boost injection pressure, changing equivalence ratio, utilizing ignition improver or fuel additives and exhaust gas recirculation.

Some Researchers focused on combustion parameters in the combustion chamber and studied combustion and performance characteristics. Maurya et al. [26] did an experimental study on HCCI combustion of ethanol at intake air temperature and at various air-fuel ratios. This experiment focused on combustion parameters and observed that, the controlled combustion parameters, gives better efficiency and low emission. Agarwal et al. [27] showed experiments with various intake air temperatures ranging from 120⁰C to 160⁰C at different air-fuel ratios, for which stable HCCI combustion is achieved. In this regard, the researcher focused on the combustion parameters. As reported, that the inlet air temperature is a very delicate parameter in governing the combustion timing and hence the success of the HCCI combustion process. Swaminathan et al [28] focused on developing a single-hole nozzle with single and multiple injection strategies. The results given that the formation of the cool flame, significant change in HCCI operation. And also reported that there was a change in the brake thermal efficiency and emissions were also under control. Avinash Kumar Agarwal

Table.5 Overview of Approaches of combustion control after literature

Researcher	Utilized fuel	Technique of combustion control	Range	Advantages	Disadvantages
Maurya et al[26]	Ethanol	Intake air heating	90-120 ⁰ c	Given that the fuel conversion efficiency and low NO _x and smoke emissions	Limited to part load operation.
Agarwal et al[27]	Ethanol and methanol	Intake air heating	120-160 ⁰ c	Reduced NO _x and smoke emissions	-
Singh et al.[29]	Diesel	Varying the air/fuel ratio and EGR	λ ranging 2.56-4.95 and 0-20%	$\lambda > 3.70$ with quiet and smooth engine operation	The UHC emission was more due to poor combustion efficiency.
Subbarao et al[31]	Diesel	Premixed ratio/EGR	10-80%/ EGR 0-30%	At 80% premixed ratio and EGR at 30% gives low NO _x and smoke emissions	-
Gajendra Singh et al[32]	Biodiesel	EGR	0-30%	Lower heat rate released	Slightly increased unburned hydrocarbon and CO emissions

et al. [29] studied and investigated on combustion parameter like ignition timing using a range of experimental data with varying intake air temperature and air-fuel ratio at different engine speeds. From the investigation it was reported that, as the fuel air mixture becomes richer, and then the ignition timing is increased. Rakesh Kumar Maurya et al. [30] focused on three operating parameters and conducted experiments in different air-fuel ratio, engine speed, and load conditions. The researcher developed the cylinder pressure history of 3000 consecutive engine cycles, for investigation purpose with piezoelectric pressure sensor. Different signal smoothing device is also analysed and their results are compared. As stated, that effect of signal processing methods on combustion parameters at different engine operating conditions. Subbarao et al. [31] studied a variety of 0 to 80% premixed ratio. Experiment stated that 80% of premixed ratio with 30% EGR lower the NO_x emissions and also enhancement in IMEP, ISFC and smoke opacity with penalties in HC and CO emissions. Gajendra Singh et al. [32] did experiment on biodiesel fuelled HCCI combustion using port fuel injector fused with fuel vaporizer by EGR technique. By using biodiesel as a fuel, the heat release rate was reduced the combustion chamber and HC, CO and smoke were increased, but NO_x was reduced, because of slower, rate of evaporation of fuel. Maurya et al. [33] investigated the varieties in cycle-to-cycle process HCCI mode engine. From the investigation, it was observed that lower intake air temperatures were sufficient to ignite the rich mixtures in HCCI mode of combustion, but higher intake temperatures were desired to ignite the lean mixtures. And also observed that, the knocking tendency was increased with pressure rise at higher temperatures of intake air and rich mixtures. The experimental details of authors [26-32] is presented in Table 5.

Future Direction of research scope

- Common rail direct injection HCCI on a diesel engine using with diferent biofuels.
- Modern high-pressure, Multi-pulse diesel fuel injection strategies.

CONCLUSION

The conclusions of this review is the preparation of homogeneous mixture, and combustion phase controlling are the main objectives of investigators in HCCI combustion to escape of limited fuel-rich regions and soot emissions, promising only

by effective preparation of homogeneous mixture despite the fact controlling combustion phase is to attain higher fuel conversion efficiency.

- ❖ The port fuel injection has high amount of air fuel mixture compared to other injection approaches, but the absences start of combustion control.
- ❖ The emissions of the NO_x and soot are decreasing in all unconventional combustion modes in comparison with convectional engines; despite the fact unburned hydrocarbon and CO emissions are high in all unconventional combustion engines.
- ❖ The grouping of equivalence ratio and charge temperature resolves the auto-ignition features of the fuel designed for HCCI combustion.
- ❖ EGR can range the auto-ignition; on the other hand combustion control using reducing the heat release rate is possible.
- ❖ The variable compression ratio is utilized to change the auto-ignition for adaptable fuels, which can change by fuel blending or additives also.
- ❖ Dilution of charge prolongs the load range of HCCI engines by delaying the combustion process and it additionally enhances the BTE.
- ❖ Though, taking strict emission norms into concern and continuous enhancement of HCCI engine performance, HCCI idea will turn out to be most appropriate and worthy future innovation of effective combustion.
- ❖ By using Common rail DI-HCCI concept additional reduces the soot and NO_x emission to nearly zero level with a little lower brake fuel conversion efficiency.

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Citation: R.Jyothu Naik *et al.* (2018). A Review on Diesel Homogeneous Charge Compression Ignition Engine, J. of Advancement in Engineering and Technology, V6I4.09. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1402846.

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